

Model and Control of a Floating-Base Elastic Wrist

Giorgio Simonini^{1,2}, Franco Angelini¹, Antonio Bicchi^{1,3}, Paolo Salaris¹

Abstract—This paper presents a dynamic model and a control approach for a robotic system consisting of an elastic wrist connected to a floating base that can move and rotate in three-dimensional space. The motivation for this research stems from the fact that the elastic wrist is typically added as an end-effector to robotic manipulators, requiring the base to be non-fixed. Moreover, optimal control methods are implemented easily on simple systems that do not rely on the entire manipulator. The wrist is modeled as a Series Elastic Actuator (SEA) arm with one joint. A backstepping controller is developed, using the trajectory of the base and the wrist motor angle as inputs. The proposed controller seeks to get stability and accurate trajectory tracking despite the complexity introduced by the elastic elements.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotic wrists play a crucial role in enhancing the dexterity and adaptability of robotic systems, particularly in applications requiring precise manipulation and interaction with the environment. Over the years, several approaches have been developed to model and control robotic wrists [1], focusing on both rigid and compliant structures. Rigid wrist designs, while offering robust control and stability, often struggle in tasks requiring compliance and adaptability to external forces. In contrast, compliant wrists, which embody elastic or flexible components, are interesting due to their ability to absorb shocks and adapt to environment uncertainties, as demonstrated in [2].

In the context of compliant robotic wrists, the use of elastic joints and stiffness-based control strategies has been increasingly explored. Notably, research on variable stiffness actuators (VSAs) [3], and in general on compliance mechanisms has provided insights into the benefits of introducing elasticity into robotic joints. These studies show the potential of elastic wrists to achieve smoother behavior with their surroundings or improve the safety of human-robot interactions.

Another key aspect related to these types of wrists is the possibility of exploiting the elastic elements to store and release energy when needed, as the authors show in [4]. The European project DARKO plays an important role in this context, seeking efficiency in tasks like pick and place, and throwing. Especially in throwing, where the end-effector has to reach a certain velocity, the use of an elastic wrist can lead to better performances.

In this work, we present a simple approach to model and control a floating elastic wrist with constant and linear stiffness and one degree of freedom (DoF). The floating nature of the wrist introduces additional complexity, as it allows for free motion in multiple directions, but permits the decoupling of the

Fig. 1. Floating point elastic soft wrist

wrist system with the connected manipulator. We develop a dynamic model of the wrist using the Euler-Lagrange equations, modeling the elasticity by linear stiffness, which connects the wrist's angular position to the motor via a spring mechanism. To control the wrist's motion, we propose a backstepping controller that takes as inputs the trajectory of the floating base and the motor's angular position.

II. MODEL

In this section, the floating elastic wrist model is presented. This model is obtained from the Euler-Lagrange equation of motion (see [5]) using the base frame trajectory and the wrist angle as coordinates. The base frame is free to move and follow a trajectory $r_b \in SE(3)$ in position and orientation, meanwhile the wrist angle $\phi \in \mathbb{R}$ is the rotation of the wrist joint. Defining $q = (r_b, \phi)$ as the configuration, and $\nu_b \in \mathbb{R}^6$ as the base twist, the system dynamics is

$$M(q)\dot{\nu} + C(q, \dot{\nu})\dot{\nu} + G(q) + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ K(\phi - \theta) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\nu = [\nu_b^T, \dot{\phi}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^7$ are the system velocities, $M \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 7}$ is the positive definite mass matrix, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 7}$ is the Coriolis matrix, $G \in \mathbb{R}^7$ is the gravity vector, $K \in \mathbb{R}$ is the stiffness of the wrist joint, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ is the wrist motor angle, and $\tau_b \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the wrench at the base. Finally, define $r \in SE(3)$ as the end-effector pose, $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^6$ as the end-effector twist, and let $J \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 7}$ be the Jacobian matrix that maps the system velocities to the end-effector twist with the relation $\xi = J\nu$.

In this work, we assume that the inputs of the system are the wrist motor angle θ and the base trajectory r_b . Moreover, external forces are considered zero in order to simplify the discussion.

III. BACKSTEPPING CONTROL

Backstepping control [6] is a control methodology used in systems that can be expressed in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= f(x_1) + g(x_1)x_2, \\ \dot{x}_2 &= h(x_1, x_2) + l(x_1, x_2)u. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This work was supported in part by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreements No. 101017274 (Darko) and in part by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) in the framework of the FoReLab and CrossLab projects (Department of Excellence).

¹Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Informazione e Centro di Ricerca "Enrico Piaggio", Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56126 Pisa, Italy

²Italian Doctorate in Robotics and Intelligent Machines

³Soft Robotics for Human Cooperation and Rehabilitation, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Morego, 30, 16163 Genova, Italy
 giorgio.simonini@phd.unipi.it

The main idea is to obtain a reference by using x_2 as the control input for the first equation, then use u to bring the real x_2 to that reference.

In our case, the control problem can be divided into three steps: first, the design of a kinematic control law generates a velocity reference. Then, a dynamic part brings the actual velocity to the new desired one, using a torque reference. Finally, the motor reference on the elastic part is given in order to follow the link-side torque. The following proposition shows the overall control law and the stability proof.

Proposition. Consider the system (1). Let e_r be the Cartesian pose error, defined with the quaternion orientation error as in [7], i.e.,

$$e_r = \begin{bmatrix} p_d - p \\ \eta \varepsilon_d - \eta_d \varepsilon - \varepsilon_d \times \varepsilon \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where $p \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position, $(\eta, \varepsilon) \in (\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{R})$ are the vector and scalar part of the quaternion respectively, and $_d$ indicates desired quantities. Let also $\xi_d \in \mathbb{R}^6$ the end-effector desired twist, and let \dot{q}_r be the velocity reference, defined as

$$\dot{q}_r = J^+(\xi_d + \Lambda e_r) \quad (4)$$

where Λ is a symmetric positive definite matrix and J^\dagger is the Moore-Penrose inverse of the Jacobian matrix. With this choice, we can define the velocity error $s = \dot{q}_r - \dot{q}$, and the torque reference as

$$\tau = M\ddot{q}_r + C\dot{q}_r + G + k_d s + J^T e_r, \quad (5)$$

where τ is a fictitious control defined as

$$\tau \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \tau_b \\ K(\phi - \theta) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Finally, we can choose the trajectory r_b as the integral of the acceleration reference \ddot{q}_r and the motor angle θ as

$$\theta = \phi + K^{-1} [M\ddot{q}_r + C\dot{q}_r + G + k_d s + J^T e_r]^{[\tau]} \quad (7)$$

where the notation $[a]^{[i]}$ stands for the i -th row of the vector a . This leads to the asymptotical stability of the closed-loop system.

Proof. Defining the velocity reference as (4), we can select as candidate Lyapunov function for kinematic control

$$V(e_r) = \frac{1}{2} e_r^T e_r. \quad (8)$$

Time derivative of (8) leads to

$$\dot{V}(e_r) = -e_r^T \Lambda e_r. \quad (9)$$

By the Lyapunov theorem, we can infer asymptotic stability at the kinematic level being $V(e_r)$ positive definite time-invariant and being \dot{V} negative definite.

For the dynamic part, we can choose the Lyapunov candidate in the state-space coordinates (e_r, s) as

$$W(e_r, s, t) = V(e_r) + \frac{1}{2} s^T M s, \quad (10)$$

where $V(e_r)$ is the Lyapunov function used in the kinematic part (8). Computing the derivative we have (omitting matrix dependences for readability)

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{W} &= e_r^T \dot{e}_r + s^T M \dot{s} + \frac{1}{2} s^T \dot{M} s \\ &= e_r^T \dot{e}_r + \frac{1}{2} s^T (\dot{M} - 2C) s + s^T (M\ddot{q}_r + C\dot{q}_r + G - \tau). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since the matrix $C(q, \dot{q})$ is written in Christoffel form we have that $(\dot{M} - 2C)$ is skew-symmetric and so $\frac{1}{2} s^T (\dot{M} - 2C) s$ is zero. At this point, τ can be written as (5) and substituting (5) in (11) it is

$$\dot{W} = -e_r^T \Lambda e_r - s^T k_d s \quad (12)$$

Concluding the demonstration with asymptotic stability of the closed-loop system. Indeed, we can apply Lyapunov's theorem for time-variant systems. The system in variables (e_r, s) has a time-variant positive definite candidate, $W(e_r, s, t)$ that is limited by K_∞ function as shown in [8] and its derivative $\dot{W}(e_r, s)$ is time-invariant and negative definite. \square

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we model a floating elastic wrist with one DoF through the classical dynamic equation. Our approach aims to achieve accurate trajectory tracking at the end-effector and ensure stability by leveraging the benefits of backstepping control.

The direction of the work is to develop a framework to use the wrist to enhance the throwing capabilities of a rigid manipulator. Since rigid manipulators are usually very precise and controlled with high-stiffness feedback controllers, it is possible to decouple the trajectory of the base given by the manipulator and the DoFs of the wrist itself. Then, given this simplified model, it is easier to develop optimal control algorithms that exploit the involved elasticity.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. M. Bajaj, A. J. Spiers, and A. M. Dollar, "State of the art in artificial wrists: A review of prosthetic and robotic wrist design," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 261–277, Feb. 2019, Conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Robotics, ISSN: 1941-0468.
- [2] Y.-F. Lee, C.-Y. Chu, J.-Y. Xu, and C.-C. Lan, "A humanoid robotic wrist with two-dimensional series elastic actuation for accurate force/torque interaction," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 1315–1325, Jun. 2016, Conference Name: IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics, ISSN: 1941-014X.
- [3] S. Wolf, G. Grioli, O. Eiberger, *et al.*, "Variable stiffness actuators: Review on design and components," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 2418–2430, Oct. 2016, Conference Name: IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics, ISSN: 1941-014X.
- [4] M. Garabini, A. Passaglia, F. Belo, P. Salaris, and A. Bicchi, "Optimality principles in stiffness control: The VSA kick," in *2012 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, ISSN: 1050-4729, May 2012, pp. 3341–3346.
- [5] J. Hollerbach, W. Khalil, and M. Gautier, "Dynamics," in *Springer Handbook of Robotics*, B. Siciliano and O. Khatib, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2008, pp. 37–66, ISBN: 978-3-540-30301-5.
- [6] H. Khalil, *Nonlinear Systems* (Pearson Education). Prentice Hall, 2002, pp. 589–603, ISBN: 9780130673893.
- [7] S. Chiaverini and B. Siciliano, "The unit quaternion: A useful tool for inverse kinematics of robot manipulators," *Systems Analysis Modelling Simulation*, vol. 35, pp. 45–60, May 1, 1999.
- [8] H. Khalil, *Nonlinear Systems* (Pearson Education). Prentice Hall, 2002, pp. 111–181, ISBN: 9780130673893.